

Action of Chlorine and Bromine on Coumarin-4- and Coumarin-3-acetic Acids : Coumarin-3- and -4-halogenoacetic Acids and 4-Halogenomethylcoumarins.

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Coumarin-3 and 4-acetic acids comprise within their molecules a double bond between carbon atoms 3 and 4 in the pyrone ring and a reactive methylene group attached to either of these atoms. A study of the action of chlorine and bromine on these acids was, therefore, expected to yield results of considerable interest by revealing the relative affinities for halogen of the methylene group and the ethenoid linkage. If the usual rule of the halogen attacking primarily the double bond in the pyrone ring were followed in this case without the interference of any possible influence exerted by the reactive methylene groups, an unstable dihalide readily changing, in the case of the coumarin-4-acetic acids into the 3-halogeno acid and in the case of the coumarin-3-acetic acids into the 4-halogeno acids should result thus:—

It is to be noted, however, that if the induced polarities of carbon atoms 3 and 4 in the crotonoid system $-\overset{+}{\text{C}}\text{H}=\overset{-}{\text{C}}\text{H}-\overset{+}{\text{C}}=\overset{-}{\text{O}}$, contained in coumarins be taken into account, they would be expected to influence materially these reactions and diminish greatly the probability of bromine being added to the double bond, particularly in coumarin-3-acetic acids.

Preliminary experiments showed that there was very little action at laboratory temperatures and exposure to direct sunlight did not effect any improvement. The best results were obtained by heating in glacial acetic acid at the temperature of the boiling water bath though in the case of the coumarin-4-acetic acids, a considerable amount of decarboxylation ensued and the product, a mixture of the halogenated acid and the decarboxylated body, had to be separated finally by cold sodium carbonate. It was observed as a general rule that decarboxylation occurred to a smaller extent with the chloro than with the bromo acids, the neutral compound being the main product obtained in the latter case under the conditions of experiment. β -Naphthopyrone-4-acetic acid provided the only exceptional case in which neither chlorination nor bromination caused any appreciable decarboxylation, but the product in this case is differently constituted. The halogenation of the coumarin-3-acetic acids was found to proceed much more slowly, a period of 5-6 hours' heating at 100° being normally required for completing the reaction. There was, however, no decarboxylation in this case and the product dissolved completely in cold sodium carbonate. This is to be explained by the superior stability of the 3-acetic acids which unlike the 4-acetic acids, do not decompose even at their melting points (*cf.* Dey and Sankaranarayanan, *loc. cit.*).

The halogenated acids, as is to be expected, proved to be stronger acids than the parent compounds; while the latter were easily liberated from a solution of their sodium salts by dilute acetic acids, the halogenated bodies did not separate from the alkaline solutions until they were treated with mineral acids. This difference has been utilised in working out an excellent method of separating a mixture of the two acids. The halogenocoumarin-4-acetic acids decomposed at their melting points quantitatively into CO₂ and halogeno-4-methylcoumarins which were found in every case to be identical with the product, insoluble in sodium carbonate, obtained during halogenation. These were neutral compounds, very sparingly soluble in boil-

ing alcohol and having an irritant action on the skin. Nascent hydrogen (zinc-copper couple) reduced them to the 4-methylcoumarins, the replacement of halogen by hydrogen occurring smoothly and quantitatively.

The position of the halogen in the products is deduced from the following considerations: That the halogen could not have entered the benzene ring is proved by (a) their behaviour with boiling aqueous alkali which completely removes the halogen, and (b) oxidation, halogen-free salicylic and hydroxynaphthoic acids or their homologues being formed. Their remains little doubt, therefore, that the halogen has either entered the pyrone ring or substituted one of the methylene hydrogen atoms, the following alternative structures for the halogenated coumarin-4-acetic acids thus becoming possible:—

(I)

(II)

It has been easy to decide between these two constitutions by studying the products obtained by (a) decomposition at their melting points and (b) heating with alkalis. The compounds formed by loss of CO_2 were found to be quite different from the 3-halogeno-4-methylcoumarins which have been prepared directly from 4-methylcoumarins by treatment with halogens (Simonis and Wenzel, *Ber.*, 1900, 33, 1961; Fries and Lindemann, *Annalen*, 1914, 404, 65; Dey and Dalal, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 3386) and also in a few cases by condensation of a phenol with α -chloroacetoacetic ester (Dey, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1606). Thus, while 3-bromo-4-methylcoumarin (Simonis and Peters, *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 832) melted at 115° , the bromo-4-methylcoumarin obtained by decarboxylation of the bromocoumarin-4-acetic acid was found to melt at 176° , similarly 3-bromo-4-methyl- α -naphthapyrone (Dey, *loc. cit.*) melted at 232° , while the corresponding product of decarboxylation of the α -naphthapyrone-4-acetic acid derivative melted at 197° , the melting points being considerably lowered in both cases by admixture.

A clearer proof of the view that the halogen atoms were not attached to position 3 in the pyrone ring is derived from a study of

the action of alkalis on these compounds. The products were well crystallised unsaturated acids isomeric with, but quite different from the benzfuran-2-carboxylic acids which have been prepared from the 3-halogenated coumarins. Structure (I) must therefore be accepted for these acids.

$\beta\alpha$ -1:2-Naphthapyrone-4-acetic acid forms, however, a solitary exception to this general rule. A careful examination of the product obtained by decarboxylating the halogenated acid showed that it was not the hydrogen atom of the reactive methylene group but that attached to the carbon atom 3 which had been replaced by halogen. The bromo- β -naphthapyrone-4-acetic acid decomposed on melting into a bromo-4-methylcoumarin which crystallised from alcohol in needles (m. p. 146°), not depressed by admixture with an authentic specimen of 3-bromo-4-methyl- $\beta\alpha$ -1:2-naphthapyrone (Bacovescu, *Ber.*, 1910, 43, 1280). Similarly, the product of chlorination of β -naphthapyrone-4-acetic acid yielded on decomposition a product (m.p. 137°), which was identified as 3-chloro-4-methyl- $\beta\alpha$ -1:2-naphthapyrone by preparing a specimen of the latter by the condensation of β -naphthol with ethyl α -chloroacetoacetate in presence of sulphuric acid and determining the mixed melting point. Moreover, the results of alkali treatment of these bodies are in complete accord with the theory that they are 3-halogenocoumarins. Thus, the chloro derivative gave a mixture of 3-chloromethyl- β -naphthacoumarinic acid (m.p. 149°) (Dey, *loc. cit.*) and 3-methyl- β -naphthafuran-2-carboxylic acid (m.p. 240°) (Dey and Lakshminarayanan, *private communication*), while the bromo derivative yielded the same furancarboxylic acid (m.p. 242°) together with a product melting at 134° which has been shown (Dey and Lakshminarayanan, *private communication*) to be 2-hydroxynaphthyl- α -propionic aldehyde. The evidence is summarised in the following scheme.

It is perfectly certain, therefore, that there is a sharp difference between β -naphthopyrone-4-acetic acid and all the other coumarin-4-acetic acids examined in this paper, this being the only instance in which the ethenoid group and not the active methylene group has been found to be attacked by the halogen. We have only to record this fact for the present and wait further observations before attempting to offer an explanation of this phenomenon.

We must in this connection correct an error which has found its way into literature regarding the nature of the product obtained by chlorinating 6-methylcoumarin-4-acetic acid (Dey, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1635). The conditions of experiment were practically the same as those adopted by us, but although the melting points of the products agree closely with those obtained in the present investigation, the conclusion that they were 3-chloro derivatives is obviously wrong as they have now been definitely proved to be 6-methylcoumarin-4-chloroacetic acid and 6-methyl-4-chloromethylcoumarin respectively. The product (m. p. 244°) obtained by boiling this chloro-acid with alkali, too, is not the 2-carboxy-5-methylbenzofuran-3-acetic acid as recorded in literature (Dey, *loc. cit.*) but must now be regarded as a member of the isomeric dihydrofuran derivative having the following structure :

The formation of these dihydrofuran acids from the coumarin-4-chloro- and bromoacetic acids and from the 4-chloro- and 4-bromomethylcoumarins has been extensively studied and the mechanism of the reaction completely elucidated. By analogy to the action of alkali on 3-halogenocoumarins, the process is to be represented as follows :

They form dimethyl and diethyl esters readily, instantly decolourise alkaline permanganate and take up 2 atoms of hydrogen when reduced catalytically in the presence of platinum oxide. The 4-chloro- and 4-bromomethylcoumarins are similarly converted into unsaturated monocarboxylic acids (A).

These yield monoalkyl esters and anilides and are readily hydrogenated to the saturated acids. The results of analyses and determination of molecular weights, as well as their chemical behaviour leave little room for doubt regarding the constitutions assigned to them and the mechanism of the reaction which gives rise to them. They have to be regarded as dihydrofuranone derivative and have been designated as 2-carboxydihydrofuranonyl-3-acetic acids and dihydrofuranonyl-3-acetic acids respectively. Attempts to convert them into the corresponding ketone or furanones by oxidation under various conditions were, however, unsuccessful, the molecules being completely broken up during the process. It is not improbable that the difficulty in getting the expected furanone arises from the presence of the characteristic glutaconic system which might cause a tautomerism of the following type in these acids.

Several unsuccessful attempts were made to confirm the constitutions of the 4-halogenomethylcoumarins and hence of the coumarin-4-halogenoacetic acids by other methods and a brief reference to some of the more important of these would not be out of place here.

The action of potassium cyanide was examined with the object of preparing the methocyanide, the subsequent hydrolysis of which to the coumarin-4-acetic acids might settle the constitution of the halogeno-4-methylcoumarins thus :

The reaction was presumably complicated by the simultaneous addition of the reagent to the double bond and no crystalline material could be isolated from the unpurifiable resinous mass which was always produced.

Several attempts were made to replace the halogen by OH, NH₂ and C₆H₅·NH groups by treatment with appropriate reagents but

they were all unsuccessful. The halogen seems to be held very firmly and not a trace of it was removed even on heating with moist silver oxide at 100° for 8 hours. In contrast with this is the behaviour with aqueous alkali which eliminates the halogen completely in the course of a few minutes. The difference is obviously to be explained by the fact that the alkali does not initially attack the bromine but that it is the pyrone ring which is first opened up, the subsequent rearrangement to the stable benzodihydrofuran ring involving the interaction of the bromine and the phenolic hydrogen. The preparation of compounds of the Grignard type with magnesium in dry ether was also attempted without success.

The oxidation of the 4-halogenomethylcoumarins to the halogen-free salicylic and hydroxynaphthoic acids has, however, been successfully accomplished, almost theoretical yields being obtained by carrying out the oxidation with permanganate in acetone solution. Similarly, reduction with nascent hydrogen was found to succeed best on refluxing an aqueous acetone solution of the substance with zinc-copper couple, the corresponding 4-methylcoumarins being obtained in quantitative yield. Experiments are now in progress for synthesising these halogenomethylcoumarins by the condensation of phenols with γ -halogenoacetoacetic ester and thereby obtaining conclusive evidence of their constitution. The results will be communicated very shortly.

The monohalogenocoumarin-3-acetic acids are on the same grounds believed to be similarly constituted, the methylene hydrogen atom being replaced by halogen. These acids are very stable and cannot be decarboxylated in the usual way into the corresponding methochloride or methobromide. The oxidation to the halogen-free salicylic acids and reduction to the parent coumarin-3-acetic acids are, however, readily effected, and the halogen is as easily eliminated by boiling alkali as in the case of the corresponding 4-acetic acid derivatives. Attempts will be made to synthesise similar products from phenols and α -aceto- α' -chlorosuccinic ester.

The action of alkali on these acids is very interesting, the compounds formed being regarded as benzpyrane derivatives. A dicarboxylic acid should normally be produced, but one of the two carboxyl groups, most probably the one attached to position-8 which is known to be unstable, loses CO₂ and a monocarboxylic acid results. Analysis, molecular weight determination and the general

chemical properties of the acids are in complete agreement with the formula given.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The coumarin-4-acetic acids were prepared directly from citric acid by the method developed in an earlier investigation (Dey and Row, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 110).

7-Methylcoumarin-4-acetic acid.—9 G. of this acid (m. p. 190°), 4 g. of 4:7-dimethylcoumarin (m. p. 134°) and another product crystallising from acetic acid in stout needles (m. p. 210°) were generally obtained from a mixture of citric acid (24 g.), *m*-cresol (10 g.) and sulphuric acid (32+15 c.c.).

7-methylcoumarin-4-bromoacetic acid.—The uncrystallised acid (4 g.) was heated with a 50 % solution of bromine in glacial acetic acid (7 c.c.) on the boiling water-bath for about 45 minutes. There was copious evolution of HBr and the solution which became clear and almost colourless deposited on cooling 3.9 g. of crystals. The major portion of this dissolved in cold sodium bicarbonate leaving an insoluble residue which after washing with alcohol, weighed 1.5 g., m.p., $227-28^\circ$. The clear filtrate was carefully acidified with acetic acid, the turbid liquid filtered again and dilute hydrochloric acid added when the bromo acid slowly separated out, yield 2.3 g. Crystallisation from 50 % alcohol (charcoal) gave clusters of colourless rods, m.p. 223° . It is insoluble in water but dissolves readily in alcohol, acetic acid and other common organic solvents. (Found: C, 48.6; H, 2.84; M.W., 294.9. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{O}_4\text{Br}$ requires C, 48.5; H, 3.0 per cent. M.W., 297).

The *ethyl ester* was prepared by saturating the alcoholic solution of the acid with dry HCl, pouring into water, washing the precipitated solid with cold sodium carbonate and crystallising from alcohol. Colourless needles, m. p. 144°. (Found: C, 51.62; H, 3.97. $C_{14}H_{13}O_4$ Br requires C, 51.69; H, 4.0 per cent).

The *methyl ester* separates from hot methyl alcohol in colourless stout needles, m. p. 162°. (Found: C, 50.07; H, 3.50. $C_{13}H_{11}O_4$ Br requires C, 50.1; H, 3.54 per cent).

6-Methyl-2-carboxydihydrofuranonyl-3-acetic acid.—The bromo acid (2 g.) was boiled for an hour with caustic potash (6 g. in 20 c. c. water) and the clear yellow solution cooled and acidified. The white precipitate was purified by reprecipitating from a cold bicarbonate solution and crystallising twice from boiling water as colourless needles, m. p. 231°, yield 1.4 g. The acid is very soluble in alcohol and acetic acid and sparingly soluble in hot water. It is quite stable and does not decompose at its melting point. (Found: C, 61.27; H, 4.32; M. W., 232.2. $C_{12}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 61.55; H, 4.27 per cent. M. W., 234).

The *diethyl ester*, prepared in the usual way, separated from dilute alcohol in soft needles, m. p. 118°. (Found: C, 66.34; H, 6.12. $C_{16}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 66.21; H, 6.21 per cent).

The *dimethyl ester* crystallised in slender needles, m. p. 83°. It is rather easily hydrolysed to the acid (m. p. 231°) by dilute alkali. (Found: C, 64.22; H, 5.22. $C_{14}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 64.12; H, 5.34 per cent).

7-Methyl-4-bromomethylcoumarin.—(a) From the decomposition of 7-methylcoumarin-4-bromoacetic acid. The acid (1 g.) was heated to 225-30° until the melt became clear and free from bubbles. The product was washed with sodium carbonate and alcohol and finally crystallised from boiling acetic acid as shining plates, m. p. 236°.

(b) From the product of direct bromination of 7-methylcoumarin-4-acetic acid. The insoluble residue, m. p. 227-28° (*vide supra*) was found to be practically pure 7-methyl-4-bromomethylcoumarin. Crystallisation from acetic acid furnished colourless plates, m. p. 236° not depressed by admixture with the other product. The substance is remarkably stable and on heating sublimed in the cooler parts as fine needles. (Found: C, 52.30; H, 3.47; Br, 31.42. $C_{11}H_9O_2$ Br requires C, 52.2; H, 3.56; Br, 31.60 per cent).

6-Methyldihydrofuranonyl-3-acetic acid.—The clear yellow solution obtained on boiling the bromomethylcoumarin (1 g.) with 30% KOH

(10 c. c.) was cooled in ice and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The product separated out slowly in snow white needles, completely soluble in sodium bicarbonate. It dissolves readily in hot water and crystallises on cooling in silky needles, m. p. 107° . It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a deep brown colour and instantly decolourises dilute permanganate and bromine water in the cold. It is very stable and melts on heating to a clear liquid without decomposition; after fusion with KOH and a few drops of water at 200° the acid is recovered unchanged. The barium, calcium and silver salts are sparingly soluble, while the methyl and ethyl esters are obtained as sweet smelling liquids insoluble in alkali. [Found: C, 69.31; H, 5.22; M. W., 189. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 69.05; H, 5.26 per cent. M. W., 190. Ag (in silver salt), 36.21. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{O}_3$ Ag requires Ag, 36.35 per cent].

The *anilide* crystallised from hot alcohol as long needles, m. p. 161° . (Found: N, 5.53. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_2\text{N}$ requires N, 5.3 per cent).

Catalytic reduction of 6-methyldihydrofuranonyl-3-acetic acid: 6-Methyldihydrofuran-3-acetic acid.—Freshly prepared platinum oxide (0.1 g.) was added to a solution of the acid (0.5 g.) in alcohol (25 c. c.) and the solution shaken in contact with pure hydrogen under slight pressure until there was no further absorption (90 c. c. in about 2 hours). After filtering the platinum oxide and distilling off the alcohol from the water-bath the residual solid was crystallised from hot water in colourless glistening plates, m. p. 130° . It does not decolourise permanganate or bromine water instantaneously but only after standing for some time. (Found: C, 68.25; H, 6.29. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 68.75; H, 6.25 per cent).

Reduction of 7-methyl-4-bromomethylcoumarin to 4:7-dimethylcoumarin.—Freshly made zinc-copper couple (2 g.) was refluxed for an hour with a solution of the bromocoumarin (1 g.) in acetone (50 c. c.) and the hot solution quickly filtered. The crystals which came down on cooling melted at 130° after two crystallisations from alcohol. It was proved to be identical with 4:7-dimethylcoumarin by a mixed m. p. determination.

Oxidation of 7-methyl-4-bromomethylcoumarin.—A solution of the bromocoumarin (1 g.) in acetone (200 c. c.) was warmed to 40° and finely powdered potassium permanganate (1.3 g.) added in small quantities with vigorous shaking. The brown precipitate was filtered after 12 hours and washed twice with boiling water. The yellow filtrate, on acidifying with dilute hydrochloric acid slowly deposited the acid

which crystallised from hot water (charcoal) as colourless needles, m.p. 176°. The acid is very soluble in alcohol sparingly so in water and gives a deep violet colour with ferric chloride. It was identified with *m*-cresotinic acid, m. p. 177°. (Found: M. W., 152·8. $C_8H_8O_3$ requires M.W., 152).

7-Methylcoumarin-4-chloroacetic acid.—A solution of 7-methylcoumarin-4-acetic acid (2 g.) in hot acetic acid (30 c. c.) was treated with a stream of chlorine (generated from 0·7 g. of permanganate) on a water-bath for half an hour, the clear cold solutions poured into water and the solid collected after 2 hours and treated with dilute sodium carbonate to separate the chloro acid from the chloromethylcoumarin formed by spontaneous decarboxylation. The chloro acid crystallised from alcohol in soft needles, m.p. 170° (decomp.), yield 1 g. The residue after melting solidified and then melted at 274°. On heating the chloro acid with 20% alkali it was converted into the same carboxy-dihydrofuranonylacetic acid (m.p. 231°) which had been obtained from the bromoacid. (Found: Cl, 13·82. M. W., 249·6. $C_{12}H_9O_4Cl$ requires Cl, 14·06 per cent. M.W., 252·5).

The *methyl ester* crystallises from dilute alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 160°. (Found: C, 58·72; H, 3·98. $C_{13}H_{11}O_4Cl$ requires C, 58·53; H, 4·13 per cent).

The *ethyl ester* separates from alcohol in sheaves of needles, m.p. 158°. (Found: C, 60·02; H, 4·47. $C_{14}H_{13}O_4Cl$ requires C, 59·88; H, 4·63 per cent).

7-Methyl-4-chloromethylcoumarin.—The spontaneously decarboxylated product obtained during the chlorination (0·8 g.) crystallised from acetic acid in clusters of needles, m.p. 214°. Boiling alkali converted it into the 6-methyldihydrofuranonyl-3-acetic acid (m. p. 107°). (Found: Cl, 18·23. $C_{11}H_9O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 17·86 per cent).

6-Methylcoumarin-4-bromoacetic acid, prepared in the usual manner from 6-methylcoumarin-4-acetic acid, crystallises in needles, m.p. 168° (decomp.). On boiling with acetic acid and allowing to crystallise, a large amount of rectangular plates, m.p. 177°, were obtained. These were found to be the corresponding bromomethylcoumarin formed by decarboxylation, yield 1·5 g. from 4·2 g. of coumarin-acetic acid. (Found: Br, 26·4; M.W., 300·1. $C_{12}H_9O_4Br$ requires Br, 27·0 per cent. M.W., 297).

The residue insoluble in sodium carbonate obtained during bromination weighed approximately 1·1 g. Crystallisation from acetic acid gave rectangular plates, m.p. 177°. (Found: Br, 31·32. $C_{11}H_9O_2Br$ requires Br, 31·6 per cent).

6-Methyl-4-bromomethylcoumarin.—The *methyl ester* crystallised in thin needles, m.p. 170° . (Found: C, 50.32; H, 3.38. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_4\text{Br}$ requires C, 50.1; H, 3.5 per cent). The *ethyl ester*, small needles, m.p. 146° .

Action of alkali on 6-methylcoumarin-4-bromoacetic acid: 5-Methyl-2-carboxydihydrofuranonyl-3-acetic acid.—This was prepared by the usual method and crystallised from water in snow-white needles, m.p. 244° . (Found: C, 61.18; H, 4.2. M.W., 235. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 61.54; H, 4.2 per cent. M.W., 234). The *dimethyl ester*, m.p. 102° , and the *diethyl ester*, m.p. 182° , were prepared easily in the usual way.

5-Methyldihydrofuranonyl-3-acetic acid was prepared by boiling the bromocoumarin (m.p. 177°) with alkali. The acid crystallises from water in silky needles, m.p. 104° , and decolourises bromine water and permanganate instantly. (Found: M. W., 189.5. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_3$ requires M. W., 190).

Oxidation of 6-methyl-4-bromomethylcoumarin was carried out with permanganate in acetone solution, the acidified filtrate being repeatedly extracted with ether, evaporated and the residue purified by dissolving in sodium carbonate and finally crystallising from water in colourless needles, m.p. 149° , identical in all respects with *p*-cresotinic acid.

6-Methylcoumarin-4-chloroacetic acid and 6-methyl-4-chloromethylcoumarin.—1.3 G. of the chloro acid and 0.3 g. of the chloromethylcoumarin were obtained from 2 g. of the acetic acid by chlorinating in the usual way. The chloro acid crystallises from alcohol in aggregates of slender needles, m.p. 162° (decomp.). (Found: M.W., 249.4. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$ requires M. W., 252.5). The chloromethylcoumarin crystallises from acetic acid in silky needles, m.p. 149° . (Found: Cl, 16.78. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{O}_2\text{Cl}$ requires Cl, 17.0 per cent). The chloro acid and the chloromethylcoumarin yielded with hot alkalis the dihydrofuranonyl derivative melting at 244° and 104° respectively.

The *methyl ester* crystallises in thin plates, m.p. 156° . (Found: C, 58.6; H, 3.92. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$ requires C, 58.5; H, 4.13 per cent).

The *ethyl ester* crystallises in long needles, m.p. 146° . (Found: C, 60.1; H, 4.83. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$ requires C, 59.9; H, 4.63 per cent).

7-Methoxycoumarin-4-bromoacetic acid, prepared from 7-methoxycoumarin-4-acetic acid, crystallises from alcohol in rectangular plates, m.p. 168° (decomp.). (Found: M.W., 314.3. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{O}_5\text{Br}$ requires M. W., 313). *7-Methoxy-4-bromomethylcoumarin* crystallises from

excess of boiling acetic acid in flat needles, m.p. 204° . (Found: Br, 29.53. $C_{11}H_9O_3Br$ requires Br, 29.74 per cent).

6-Methoxydihydrofuranonyl-3-acetic acid, prepared from the bromomethyl derivative by boiling with 2N-alkali, crystallises from hot water in small needles, m.p. 126° . (Found: M.W., 208.4. $C_{11}H_{10}O_4$ requires M.W., 208).

Coumarin-4-bromoacetic acid was obtained from coumarin-4-acetic acid in very poor yield, the main product being the bromomethyl coumarin. It crystallises from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 135° (decomp.). (Found: C, 47.1; H, 2.4; M.W., 286.2. $C_{11}H_7O_4Br$ requires C, 46.6; H, 2.5 per cent. M.W., 283). *4-Bromomethylcoumarin* crystallises from alcohol in needles, m.p. 176° . (Found: Br, 33.1. $C_{10}H_7O_2Br$ requires Br, 33.5 per cent).

Benzodihydrofuranonyl-3-acetic acid was prepared easily by boiling 4-bromomethylcoumarin with alkali for a few minutes. It crystallises from hot water in snow-white needles, m. p. 93° , instantly decolourising permanganate and bromine water. (Found: M. W., 174.4. $C_{10}H_8O_3$ requires M. W., 176).

α -Naphthapyrone-4-bromoacetic acid crystallises from alcohol in colourless plates, m. p. 190° (decomp.), yield 1.3 g. from 5 g. of the pyrone. (Found: C, 53.6; H, 2.5. M. W., 337.8. $C_{15}H_9O_4Br$ requires C, 54.0; H, 2.7 per cent. M.W., 333).

4-Bromomethyl- α -naphthapyrone, the main product of the bromination, weighed 3 g. It crystallises from excess of glacial acetic acid in pale yellow plates, m. p. 197° . (Found: Br, 27.48. $C_{14}H_9O_2Br$ requires Br, 27.66).

α -Naphthadihydrofuranonyl-3-acetic acid crystallises from dilute alcohol in colourless needles, m. p. 130° . The silver salt was analysed. (Found: Ag, 32.33. $C_{14}H_9O_3Ag$ requires Ag, 32.43 per cent).

Oxidation of 4-bromomethyl- α -naphthapyrone.—A solution of the bromo compound (21 g.) in acetone (120 c. c.) was treated with permanganate (2.2 g.) and the oxidation allowed to proceed at the laboratory temperature for a couple of hours. The product was worked up in the usual way. Fine needles, m. p. 187° not depressed by admixture with an authentic specimen of 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid.

3-Bromo- β -1:2-naphthapyrone-4 acetic acid.—The β -1:2-naphthapyrone-4-acetic acid (5 g.) suspended in acetic acid was treated with bromine in the usual way. The product separated at first as an oil which subsequently solidified to a yellow crystalline mass com-

pletely soluble in sodium carbonate. Crystallisation from alcohol gave shining yellow needles, m. p. 188° (decomp.), yield 2.7g. (Found: C, 53.8; H, 2.81. C₁₅H₉O₄ Br requires C, 54.1; H, 2.7 per cent).

The *methyl ester* crystallises in soft needles, m. p. 172°. (Found: Br, 23.66. C₁₆H₁₁O₄ Br requires Br, 23.03 per cent). The *ethyl ester* crystallises in colourless rhombic plates, m. p. 139°.

3-Bromo-4-methyl-βa-1:2-naphthapyrone.—The bromoacetic acid was heated to 200° when the acid completely melted with effervescence. The solid residue was washed with sodium carbonate and crystallised from alcohol as colourless plates, m. p. 146°, not depressed by admixture with a specimen of 3-bromo-4-methyl-βa-1:2-naphthapyrone obtained by the direct bromination of the naphthapyrone.

2-Carboxy-β-naphthafuran-3-acetic acid.—The bromo acid was boiled for an hour under reflux with 2N-NaOH the clear alkaline solution cooled and acidified and the solid crystallised from alcohol as colourless rectangular plates, m. p. 252° (decomp.). It does not decolourise permanganate and bromine water instantly as in the case with the furanonyl acetic acids. (Found: M. W., 263.2. C₁₅H₁₀O₅ requires M. W., 270). On heating a pinch of the acid with resorcinol and sulphuric acid pouring into water and adding alkali bright green fluorescence is developed. The *dimethyl ester* crystallises from alcohol in square plates, m.p. 158°. The *diethyl ester* forms shining plates, m. p. 104°.

3-Chloro-βa-1:2-naphthapyrone-4-acetic acid, prepared by chlorination in the usual way, crystallises from acetic acid in yellow plates, m. p. 152° (decomp.), yield 1.5 g. from 2.5 g. of the acid. (Found: M. W., 291.6. C₁₅H₉O₄ Cl requires M. W., 288.5). The *ethyl ester* crystallises in plates, m. p. 134°.

3-Chloro-4-methyl-βa-1:2-naphthapyrone, obtained by heating the above acid to 160-73° crystallises from boiling alcohol in stout needles, m. p. 137°, not depressed by admixture with a specimen synthesised from β-naphthol and α-chloroacetoacetic ester by Pechmann's method.

The chloro acid and the 3-chloronaphthapyrone were converted by hot alkali into the carboxyfuranacetic acid (m. p. 252°) and the furancarboxylic acid (m.p. 242°) respectively. The latter was mixed, however, with the coumarinic acid (m. p. 149°).

Coumarin-3-bromoacetic acid.—Comarin-3-acetic acid (4 g.), suspended in glacial acetic acid (15 c.c.) was treated with a 50% solution of bromine in acetic acid (7 c. c.) in the usual way. The resulting solid consisted entirely of the bromoacetic acid. It crystallises from acetic acid in glistening plates, m. p. 200°. The acid is remarkably stable and shows no signs of decomposition when heated considerably above its melting point. (Found: C, 46.1; H, 2.6; M. W., 279.7. $C_{11}H_7O_4Br$ requires C, 46.64; H, 2.5 per cent. M. W. 283.0).

The *methyl ester* crystallises in colourless needles, m. p. 94°. (Found: C, 48.5; H, 3.21. $C_{12}H_9O_4Br$ requires C, 48.5; H, 3.03 per cent).

Benzopyran-2-carboxylic acid.—The bromoacetic acid (2 g.) was boiled for half an hour with 2N-KOH and the colourless potassium salt which slowly separated out was dissolved in water. The solid obtained on acidification crystallises from dilute alcohol in rectangular plates, m. p. 142°. It does not decolourise immediately bromine or permanganate. (Found: C, 68.0; H, 4.71. $C_{10}H_8O_3$ requires C, 68.2; H, 4.55 per cent). The silver salt was analysed. (Found: Ag, 37.81. $C_{10}H_7O_3 Ag$ requires Ag, 38.16 per cent).

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